

OVERSHOT WATERWHEEL GENERATOR AT BARANGAY BONFAL WEST, BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to design and construct an overshot waterwheel generator at Colocol Irrigation on Barangay Bonfal West, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, capable of supplying streetlights on a minor road in the area. The researchers observed that Colocol Irrigation has the potential to become a source of energy that benefits the community; hence, a prototype of an overshot waterwheel generator was presented. The testing site was a channel beside the sluice gate of the Colocol Irrigation. The testing was conducted three times a day for 4 consecutive days, and valuable data were collected. The result shows that a maximum of 30 volts dc can be generated and a current of 8.31 amperes for a stable supply load of 250 watts because the generated voltage is higher than 30 volts dc causes the inverter to shut down due to overvoltage, and the lowest generated voltage was 22.2 volts dc and a current of 2.25 amperes that supply a load of 50 watts. Still, no data was collected when the water level was too low to reach the turbine. The output load was represented by 25-watt lightbulbs connected in parallel, and the voltage was measured using the voltmeter reading on the inverter. At the same time, the current was determined using the power formula. The overshot waterwheel has shown potential for further development to harness the Colocol Irrigation as a renewable source of energy in the area.

Keywords: Overshot waterwheel, generator, renewable energy, colocol irrigation

INTRODUCTION

The demand for energy around the world has been increasing due to the growing population as well as the rapid development of civilization, which also results in the increasing use of fossil fuels for energy production. Despite not being sustainable with serious environmental and health issues, fossil fuels remain the primary source of energy (Olabi, A. G., & Abdelkareem, M. A., 2022).

Brahim, S. P. (2014) also states that in terms of global final energy consumption, fossil fuels continue to be the main source of energy despite the constant contribution of renewable energy. However, many countries were driven to seek and develop other energy sources due to many reasons, such as depleting fossil fuels, environmental impacts, climate change, volatility of oil prices, and pollution caused by the use of fossil fuels. Renewable resources such as solar, hydro, wind, and geothermal show great potential in this aspect, and because of this, renewable energy has become a major part of many countries' energy agendas in an effort to maintain energy sustainability and security.

In the Philippines, the government carried out policies and set short and long-term renewable energy goals to support the development of renewable energy in the country. Aside from its goal of achieving energy security and self-sufficiency, the country's goal is to become a leading figure in geothermal energy, the largest wind power user, and the solar manufacturing hub, which is what drives these efforts. The country's share of renewable energy in the following years is expected to increase with these established goals and policies (Brahim, S. P., 2014).

By the year 2030, the Philippines energy plan has set a goal in its power energy mix consisting of 70% generating capacity using coal, biomass, hydro power and nuclear, a 20% capacity generated from natural gas and a capacity of 10% using oil-based plant as well as variable renewable energy like wind and solar (Gulagi et al., 2021).

In the northern part of the Philippines, the province of Nueva Vizcaya, situated in Luzon, is said to be 79% mountainous, distinguished by steep to very steep landform, 8% rolling to moderately steep, and 13% undulating to rolling, gently sloping to undulating and flat to near flat. Given its rocky terrain, the province developed intricate water raceways like rivers, creeks, streams, and springs, according to the province's official website. Along with small irrigations, the province provides suitable locations for small hydro power generation.

Hydroelectric power plants are commonly situated at nearby water sources where water is guided through a pipe or penstock to a turbine, which causes it to spin and is used to produce electricity. The energy that can be harnessed in moving water can be determined depending on the volume of flowing water and the head of water, according to the U.S. Energy Information Administration (2023).

In this modern time, waterwheels are basically slow-running hydro power machines, which are most suitable for locations with low-head water that also do not rely on technical irrigation systems. Historically, there have been four known waterwheels, namely Undershot, Breastshot, Overshot, and Pitchback/Backshot waterwheels (Basar et al., 2024).

Whereas this particular study aims to design an overshot waterwheel, it can be used for irrigation at the proposed location and generate power to supply streetlights.

Figure 1.1
Waterwheel Types

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1515/ehs-2023-0138>

A. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.2
Prototype Architecture

This system harnesses the natural energy of flowing water to spin a wheel, which powers a generator. The generator produces electricity that flows through a DC regulator, ensuring a stable voltage supply even during grid fluctuations or temperature changes in the load. To expand its functionality, we incorporated an inverter that seamlessly converts the steady DC into versatile AC power suitable for various applications. Additionally, the system includes a smart photosensor that optimizes energy efficiency by automatically switching the lights off during daylight hours and turning them on when darkness falls, ensuring reliable, eco-friendly operation.

B. Statement of the Problem

The rural areas in some portions of Nueva Vizcaya do not have enough street lights to illuminate the streets for vehicles passing by. One example of this is the road beside Colocol Irrigation at Barangay Bonfal West, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. To address this problem, the researchers will design and build an Overshoot waterwheel that will utilize the flow of water on the irrigation to be used as renewable energy for energy harvesting and generate electricity to power streetlights in the area.

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The method used in this study includes information gathering, illustrating, and interpreting data, which will be used in the design. Necessary data, such as water head

and channel width, will be gathered to design the prototype of an overshot waterwheel

Figure 2.1
Site Location

Source: *Google Maps*

through SketchUp. The prototype will then be tested and evaluated. Tables, figures, and layout plans will be used to present the data results and design.

B. Research Environment

The study will be conducted at an irrigation called Colocol Irrigation Canal located in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. A part of that irrigation stretch passes through Brgy. Don Mariano Marcos, Brgy. Sta. Rosa and Brgy. Bonfal West has a single-lane minor road alongside it. The irrigation has two gates, one located at Sta. Rosa and one at Bonfal West.

The researchers chose the gate situated at Barangay Bonfal West, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, for this study because of its higher flow rate based on ocular observation. This particular gate is just behind Muir Woods Academy and the GT Oil Gasoline Station, as shown in **Figure 2.1**. The area also faces challenges in providing reliable and eco-friendly street lighting. By harnessing the natural flow of water in the irrigation, the system provides continuous, clean energy, benefiting the community and serving as a model for other rural areas.

C. Research Instrument

To design and create a prototype of an Overshot waterwheel, the researchers use the following instruments:

Sketch up - used to design a 3D model for the Overshot waterwheel. It will also be used to design a 3D representation of the site development plan for streetlights in the area.

AutoCAD is used to create 2D designs for streetlights and layout plans for the study.

Microsoft Word is used for editing and creating related paperwork.

Tape measure - used to measure the dimensions of the channel.

Multimeter - used to measure the electrical values produced by the prototype

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers will build and design a 3D model of an Overshot waterwheel that can create an efficient energy harvesting system and generate electricity to power the streetlights. Also, the researchers will make a plan for the streetlight at the location. The

researchers will have time and effort to gather reliable sources to ensure the reliability of their study.

To achieve the creation of an Overshot waterwheel generator, the following steps were noted:

Figure 2.2

Data Gathering Procedure

RESULTS

A. Site Visitation and Data Gathering

Figure 3.1

Gate 2 at Bonfal West, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Surveying the site allows the researchers to choose an appropriate location for testing and properly design a prototype that fits the chosen testing location.

The testing site is a part of the long Colocol Irrigation Canal stretching from Brgy. Don Mariano Marcos to Brgy. Bonfal West, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The irrigation canal has a minor road beside it and two sluice gates, which will be referred to as sluice gate 1 and sluice gate 2, respectively, that control the water flow. The sluice gate 1 is located at Brgy. Sta Rosa, while the sluice gate 2 is located at Brgy. Bonfal West.

Upon observation, the researchers deemed that the sluice gate 2, as shown in **Figure 3.1**, which is located at Brgy. Bonfal West is the most suitable spot to conduct the study because the flow of water is visibly stronger, and it is easier to access.

After the observation, the researchers gathered data such as the width and height of the channel, which is important for the design of the prototype. The day of the data gathering happened to be rice harvesting season, and the planting season followed, so no water was flowing in the channel. The researchers took this chance to measure the width and height of the channel. The channel width was measured from top, middle, and bottom, and the results are approximately 186 cm, 187 cm, and 190 cm, respectively. The depth of the channel is measured at approximately 117 cm. These data are important to determine the dimension of the prototype so that it fits the channel. The minor road measures a span of 1km.

Figure 3.2
Data Gathering

B. Computation and Evaluation of Gathered Data

Power Consumption of Streetlights

LOAD	POWER	QUANTITY	TOTAL POWER
Streetlights	30 watts	50	1500 watts

The power that could be generated theoretically in the flow of water that feeds the turbine can be calculated using the following formula:

$$P_{th} = \rho q g H$$

Where;

- P_{th} = Theoretical Power (W)
- ρ = density of water (1000 kg/m³)
- q = flow rate of water (m³/s)
- g = gravitational constant (9.81m/s²)
- H = head (m)

The theoretical power that the generator must extract to supply the streetlights with a net power capacity of 1500 watts can be calculated as:

$$P_{th} = P_{load} / 80\%$$

$$P_{th} = 1500 / 80\%$$

$$P_{th} = \mathbf{1,875\ W}$$

To account for the losses, the generator can only produce 80% of its capacity, so the load will be divided by 0.8 so that we can calculate the theoretical power capacity.

Streetlight Development Plan

The researchers aim to illuminate a span of 1 km of a minor road; a total of 50 streetlights were placed in a one-sided arrangement. Each streetlight will be placed at 10 m-40 m apart in accordance with the *DOE Roadway Lighting Guideline*, but as the road to be illuminated has a width of less than 4m, the researchers rescaled the height of the streetlight, mass arm length, and its wattage.

Figure 3.3a
DOE Roadway Lighting Guidelines

Road	Road Width, meters	Arrangement	Lamp Wattage, Watts	Luminaire Spacing, Meters	Mounting Height, meters	Mast Arm Length, meters
Expressway	10	Twin Central	250	25-35	12	1.5
	15		250	20-35	12	3.0
	20	Opposite	250	20-45	12	1.5
	25		250	20-40	12	1.5
	30		250	20-30	12	1.5
	36		250	20-25	12	1.5
	40		250	20-22	12	1.5
Major	10	One-side	250	10-40	10	1.5
	15	Twin Central	250	10-45	12	3.0
	10		150	20-37	10	1.5
	15		250	20-43	12	3.0
	20	Opposite	150	20-40	10	3.0
	25		250	20-45	10	1.5
	30		250	20-45	10	1.5
	36		250	20-45	12	3.0
	40		250	20-45	12	3.0
	Collector	10	One-side	150	10-40	10
15		250		10-50	12	3.0
10		Twin Central	150	20-40	10	1.5
15			150	20-37	12	3.0

Source: *legacy.doe.gov.ph*

Figure 3.3b
DOE Roadway Lighting Guidelines

Road	Road Width, meters	Arrangement	Lamp Wattage, Watts	Luminaire Spacing, meters	Mounting Height, meters	Mast Arm Length, Meters
Collector	20	Opposite	150	20-47	10	1.5
	25		250	20-48	10	1.5
Rural Highway	8	One-side	150	10-38	8	1.5
	10		150	10-37	8	3.0
	15		150	15-38	10	3.0
	10	Twin Central	150	20-45	10	3.0
	15	Opposite	150	20-39	12	3.0
	20		150	20-45	8	1.5
Minor	4	One-side	70	10-40	8	1.5
	6		70	10-40	8	1.5
	8		70	10-40	8	1.5
	10		70	10-39	8	1.5
	10	Twin Central	70	20-35	8	1.5
	15	Staggered	70	10-20	8	1.5
	15	Opposite	70	20-40	8	1.5

Source: *legacy.doe.gov.ph*

Streetlight Specification

Figure 3.4
Streetlight Specification

Figure 3.5a
Streetlight Model

Figure 3.5b
Streetlight Model

Based on the *DOE Roadway Lighting Guideline* for minor roads as shown in **Figure 3.3b**, the mounting height should be 8 meters. Still, as the road to be illuminated has a width of less than 4m, the researchers rescaled the height of the streetlight and mast arm length. Therefore, the streetlights were designed to have a height of 4.5m and a mast arm length of .5m. Based on available materials, a mini streetlight with a wattage of 30 watts and 3300 lumen output will be used.

Illumination Requirements

To calculate the illumination required by the streetlights, the following formula is used:

$$E = (Al \times cu \times mf) / w \times d$$

Where;

- E = Horizontal Illumination level
- Al = Average illumination
- cu= coefficient of utilization
- mf= maintenance factor
- w = road width
- d = distance between fixtures

The road to be illuminated has a classification of light pedestrian traffic and very light vehicular traffic, so the following parameters will be used to calculate the illumination:

$$E = 2.15; cu = .29; mf = .8; w = 4; d = 25\text{mtrs.}$$

So, the average illumination is calculated as:

$$Al = (E \times w \times d) / cu \times mf$$

$$Al = (2.15 \times 4 \times 25) / .29 \times .8$$

$$Al = 927 \text{ lumens}$$

Based on the calculations, an LED mini streetlight with a wattage of 30 watts and a 3300 lumen output will be used.

Calculation of the actual illumination level for the chosen luminaire is shown as:

$$E = (3300 \times .29 \times .8) / 4 \times 25$$

$$E = 7.656 \text{ lumens}$$

The actual illumination level is more than that of the required value, so the chosen streetlight is more than enough to illuminate the roadway.

Figure 3.6

Recommended Average Horizontal Illumination Level

Pedestrian Traffic	Vehicular Traffic Classification			
	Very Light	Light	Medium	Heavy to heaviest
	Under 150	150-500	500 to 1200	1200 up
Heavy	9.68	12.91	16.14	21.52
Medium	6.48	8.61	10.26	12.91
Light	2.15	4.30	6.46	9.68

Source:dpwh.gov.ph/DPWH/sites/default/files/webform/civil_works/advertisement/25f10014_-_plans_part_5_of_13.pdf

C. Prototype Design and Construction

The whole prototype design is composed of 4 parts, which consist of the raceway, the frame, the turbine, the gears, and the generator. It has a height of 117 cm and a width of 141cm. The prototype was designed to specifically fit the water channel in order to achieve maximum results during the process of testing. The whole prototype was made of steel angle bars, galvanized steel sheets, A 24 Volt Dc Generator, and mechanical components such as gears and bearings.

Figure 3.8
Raceway

Figure 3.9
Frame

Figure 3.10
Turbine

Figure 3.12
Gears

Figure 3.13
24V, 350-Watt DC Generator

Figure 3.14
24V, 1000-Watt Inverter

Figure 3.15
Gear Protection

Figure 3.16
Bearing covers

D. Prototype Testing

In gathering data, the researchers conducted an open circuit test to get the voltage. They took the current by connecting a load. The load used in testing is composed of 12 pieces of 25-watt bulbs connected in parallel, attached to a piece of plywood. The researchers tested the prototype for 4 days with 3 trials each at three different timeframes.

E. Summary of Tests

After a series of tests, the data gathered has been compiled. The output power was based upon the capacity of the generator to maintain a stable supply of power to the connected loads without causing the bulbs to turn on/off. The researchers mainly relied on the voltage reading on the inverter to determine the output voltage of the generator while using the power formula to determine current on the trials. The output power was recorded during the mornings on those testing days. There are instances where the prototype was unable to produce power due to some factors, like the water level dropping too low, which cannot reach the top of the channel, and component limitations. Some factors increase the water level and flow rate, which causes the prototype to produce more power, such as sudden rain in the area.

Table 3.5
Summary of Tests

No. of Trials	Voltage	Current	Output Load
<i>Day 1 of testing</i>			
Trial 1	30 volts	8.31 amps	250 watts
Trial 2	29.6 volts	7.6 amps	225 watts
Trial 3	22.2 volts	2.25 amps	50 watts
<i>Day 2 of testing</i>			
Trial 1	33.1 volts	null	null
Trial 2	25.9 volts	6.76 amps	175 watts
Trial 3	27.2 volts	7.35 amps	200 watts
<i>Day 3 of testing</i>			
Trial 1	29.5 volts	4.24 amps	250 watts
Trial 2	null	null	null
Trial 3	null	null	null
<i>Day 4 of testing</i>			
Trial 1	23.6 volts	4.24 amps	100 watts
Trial 2	null	null	null
Trial 3	null	null	null

DISCUSSION

A. Conclusions

Using the gathered data throughout the study and carefully testing trials, the results have successfully met the following objectives of the study:

1. The researchers were able to design a site development plan for streetlights in the area by following the standard procedures and guidelines for roadway lighting.

2. The researchers were able to calculate the power consumption of the streetlights in the area in accordance with the design and the energy production of the prototype.
3. Design and construct a prototype of an overshoot waterwheel generator capable of generating power to use in streetlights.
4. Successfully test the prototype in the chosen location, providing valuable data that is analyzed to prove that the Colocol irrigation is a good potential source of energy.

B. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations aim to address issues observed throughout the study.

1. Redesign the system by adding a battery and charge controller for a consistent power supply to store energy during peak periods to be used when the water level is low.
2. Replace the inverter with a higher voltage rating to avoid overvoltage.
3. Expand the raceway so that it can completely cover the channel and direct more water into the turbine.
4. Redesign the raceway so that it can properly regulate the water that flows into the turbine.
5. Create a tightly sealed gear protector to prevent water from getting on the gears.
6. Researchers are recommended to study the design of the turbine further for maximum energy conversion.
7. Use other materials to substitute for steel. Researchers may replace other components with lighter materials as long as it does not affect its performance by a large margin to reduce the weight because the waterwheel is large and heavy.
8. Regular maintenance is needed to keep the prototype in maximum working condition.

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